

USE OF INNOVATIVE TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION**Ruzmetova Maftuna Rasulovna**

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Annotation; "innovative technology" is capable of self-development and creates conditions for the comprehensive development of all its participants, and innovative education is a developing education. In this thesis is discussed about use of innovative technologies in educational process.

Key words;*modern*, innovative, education, foreign languages,

Nowadays, there is an increasing interest and focus on incorporating cutting-edge technologies, educational methods, and informational technologies in the field of education. This trend is on the rise. A significant factor contributing to this is the contrast between traditional and modern forms of education. In the former, students are instructed to solely obtain pre-existing knowledge, whereas the latter permits them to actively seek out, scrutinize, and interpret information, ultimately cultivating the ability to form original conclusions. The teacher sets up an environment that fosters the growth, shaping, acquisition of knowledge, and character development of the person. Hence, the significance of contemporary instructional approaches, inventive teaching methodologies, and information technologies in training proficient and qualified educators cannot be undermined. This objective involves enhancing higher education by incorporating contemporary pedagogical approaches and advanced technological tools to improve educational practices. Additionally, there is a focus on promoting innovative work practices and developing community-based educational institutions that foster cooperation. The process of transforming scientific knowledge into practical innovations can be described as a step-by-step process, culminating in the dissemination of a product, service or technology.

The contemporary educational material provided to learners consists of not only the acquisition of scientific knowledge but also the cultivation of skills pertinent to contemporary knowledge methodologies. A modern approach to delivering well-structured educational content is through multimedia materials using contemporary methods of communication. Innovative teaching methods incorporate more than just absorbing information passively, they also emphasize the importance of actively developing competencies through collaborative student engagement in the learning experience. The characteristics

of education that satisfy the needs of society, individuals, and social systems are what determine the quality of education provided by the state.

The distinguishing characteristic of the novel method of education deviates from the conventional model by not restraining the self-sufficiency of learners or their scholastic pursuits, but rather guiding them towards a predetermined objective, working collaboratively in educational activities, and intentionally leading them towards tasks. This approach is believed to enhance students' curiosity in scientific fundamentals by efficiently coordinating activities without imposing a strict regimen, and permitting them to exercise free choice without stifling their wants, passions, or abilities.

In modern times, proficiency in foreign languages has become a fundamental element of education. Because specialists in diverse fields are frequently collaborating with international partners, there is a significant need for them to acquire language proficiency. The attainment of this objective is contingent upon the pragmatic approaches and competencies possessed by instructors. The educator possesses the competence to guide the education, talents, certifications, teaching materials, contemporary educational techniques to suit the objective, and he sets a particular aim for the student based on the state-mandated educational guidelines. An education model that is tailored to specific goals and objectives is designed with flexibility in mind. The model's construction primarily relies on adopting a systematic approach, establishing a set of objectives, and systematically accomplishing them in a specific order. One crucial mandate of contemporary educational technology is the development of an instructional framework. The teacher can effectively resolve targeted educational issues by utilizing a blend of various approaches. Regarding this matter, teachers and students ought to acquaint themselves with up-to-date approaches to teaching languages that are not native to them. Consequently, individuals acquire the skill of selecting the most efficient strategies to attain their objectives. The process of teaching involves taking small strides and building upon the student's pre-existing knowledge framework.

Distinct approaches are being introduced in the field of language instruction. In this scenario, students are categorized into clusters according to the level of education they are being taught, which include primary, middle, and higher education. The instructor formulates a distinctive program tailored for each level. Incorporating modern technologies into a lesson provides opportunities for a teacher to utilize myriad technical instruments, such as computers, electronic boards, projectors, and more. The greater the level of

innovation employed by a teacher, the greater the amount of content that will be generated. It is important to acknowledge that concepts pertaining to groundbreaking technology and participatory approaches in education are subject to evolution and imperfection. Individual teachers have the ability to introduce innovative ideas to the field of education. The dissatisfaction of a teacher in their work can lead to the emergence of creative and advanced technologies.

The true indication of innovation lies in its ability to produce favorable outcomes in a teacher's performance. The significance of this measure is evident in the cohesive development of an individual, encompassing their notions and comprehension. The process of innovation can be viewed as the transformation of a scientific concept into practical application, which results in changes in the social and educational milieu.

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